

HIGH PERFORMANCE HIERARCHICAL COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotubes (CNT) have been shown to be an effective reinforcement in continuous fibre composites as they improve the out-of-plane properties without degrading in-plane ones, as well as providing multifunctionality. The resulting hierarchical composites (HCs) can be produced with high CNT loadings using a powder impregnation route, but fracture toughness improvements have been modest. In this paper, a modification of the powderpregging route is presented, which allows engineering of the composite matrix microstructure to yield significant (36%) improvements in Mode I fracture toughness.

1 INTRODUCTION

Although carbon fibre composites have provided a lighter and stiffer alternative to metals in load bearing structures, their poor matrix dominated properties still complicate or restrict their structural use. Structural failure almost always initiates as delamination and/or compressive failure due to the inferior interlaminar fracture toughness and longitudinal compression strength of composite laminates relative to their in-plane properties such as tensile strength and stiffness. [1] Some of the approaches employed to improve out-of-plane properties have involved introducing toughening agents into the resin, Z-pinning, stitching and 3D composite architectures. All of these approaches have shown improvements in damage tolerance, but there have always been trade-offs usually in the form of reduced in-place properties, cost or redesign and requalification of components. [2] Incorporating thermoplastic particles in epoxy resins has been a particularly popular and successful toughening method, with commercially available third generation prepregs attaining an interlaminar fracture toughness of around 300 J/m² [3]. The drawbacks of thermoplastic toughening are reduced

compression and fatigue performance and increased sensitivity to processing [2], with the local distribution of thermoplastic particles heavily disturbed in structures such as skin-stringer elements. [4]

The addition of nanoreinforcement to continuous fibre composites has been shown to have virtually no effect on the fibre dominated properties of composite laminates, such as tensile, compressive and flexural moduli and tensile strength. [5-11] On the other hand, all matrix dominated properties have been enhanced by the addition of CNTs to the matrix: compression and flexure strength by as much as 15% and 18% [10], interlaminar shear strength by 27% [11] and Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness by 100% and 28%, respectively [12]. The particularly impressive Mode I enhancement of 100% was in a relatively brittle system with a baseline G_{IC} of 86 J/m², for which short fibre theory predicts significant toughening by debonding, pull-out, and fibre fracture. [13] By placing and aligned CNT forest in the interlaminar region of a laminate before consolidation the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS), Mode I and Mode II fracture toughnesses can even be improved by 69%, 150% and 200%, respectively [14, 15]. This approach not only requires large, highly aligned CNT forests that do not act on the intralaminar space, but it is not yet clear whether the toughening is due to the CNTs or the resin rich layer in the interlaminar region. With regards to absolute values, even for unidirectional (UD) HCs with thick CNT and resin rich interlayers the Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness values are only as high as 500-550 J/m² [3, 15], although typically in the 170-200 J/m² range for HCs manufactured using more conventional processes [16, 17] and as high as 650 J/m² when using low T_g matrices [9].

Attempts to produce HCs by reinforcing the matrix with CNTs have been plagued by processing difficulties caused by the increased matrix viscosity and nanotube infiltration. Some groups [18-20] have tried manufacturing HCs by conventional methods such as resin transfer moulding (RTM) and resin film infusion (RFI), but using matrices containing more than 1 wt% CNTs resulted in CNT agglomeration and only partial impregnation of the continuous fibres. Chen adapted the drum winding technique directly from prepreg manufacturing and produced good quality HCs containing 1.5% CNTs by volume of matrix [21]; however, this method is limited to low CNT concentration as increasing the CNT loading would render the impregnation bath too viscous for successful impregnation. Yokozeki has demonstrated the capability to produce good quality HCs in terms of homogeneity, CNT dispersion and distribution as well as mechanical and multifunctional properties using a wet impregnation route [12, 16, 22].

Previous studies have demonstrated that the mechanical and multifunctional properties of HCs can be enhanced by increasing the CNT loading in the matrix, a trend that could continue for loadings higher than 12 wt%, but has not been explored due to limitations in processing and manufacturing [23]. A wet thermoplastic powder impregnation method [24] was the inspiration for a processing route that has been developed [25] to reinforce composites with up to 20 wt% CNTs in the matrix. Due to the modest Mode I fracture toughness improvements, the impregnation process was redesigned to create a microstructurally heterogeneous matrix that induces a tortuous crack path and, as a result, enhanced fracture toughness.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

As with conventional prepregging processes, the required materials were thermosetting matrix and carbon fibre. The process by which the nanoreinforced matrix, i.e. nanocomposite, was produced involves shear mixing epoxy resin, curing agent and CNTs (NC 7000, Nanocyl®) in an extruder followed by powdering of the extrudate by VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland.

Epoxy sized Hexcel AS4C-GP® fibres in 12k tows was chosen as the carbon fibre and also generously supplied by Hexcel. The epoxy sizing not only improves compatibility with the epoxy based matrix, but also aids handling and reduces the amount of fibre damage as tows pass through the impregnation line.

To make homogeneous matrix composites, the carbon fibres were impregnated with powders containing 0, 2.4, 4.8, 9.1 and 20 wt% CNTs. For the composites with heterogeneous matrices, the

neat epoxy powder was blended with powders containing 4.8 and 13 wt% CNTs to make three systems, as detailed in Table 1.

Matrix type	Powders	Ratio	Total CNT in matrix
Hetero. 2.5 (1:1)	Neat resin, 4.8 wt% CNT	1:1	2.5 wt%
Hetero. 7.5 (1:1)	Neat resin, 13.0 wt% CNT	1:1	7.5 wt%
Hetero. 2.2 (5:1)	Neat resin, 13.0 wt% CNT	5:1	2.2 wt%

Table 1: Powder mixtures for production of heterogeneous matrix HCs.

2.2 Processing

The prepreg manufacturing was similar to that outlined in [25], except for reducing the amount of surfactant used to maintain the powder suspension (0.5 wt% of the matrix powder) and blending powders to make the heterogeneous matrix composites.

2.3 Mode I fracture toughness measurements

The Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the laminates was measured and calculated according to ASTM D5528. At least five 150 mm long and 20 mm wide specimens were cut from each laminate panel before the aluminium loading blocks (19 mm x 12 mm) were bonded to the pre-cracked ends with a room temperature curing epoxy (Araldite 2011, Huntsman®). The test was performed in the double cantilever beam (DCB) configuration. Each specimen was pre-cracked at 5 mm min⁻¹, unloaded at 5 mm min⁻¹ to zero displacement and re-loaded at 1 mm min⁻¹ to propagate the crack. Crack length was monitored with a camera and traveling stage device built in-house. G_{IC} was calculated using the corrected beam theory (CBT).

3 RESULTS

All of the manufactured composite had fibre volume fractions (v_f) between 50 and 55% and void contents less than 2 vol%, except for the homogeneous HC containing 20 wt% CNTs, which had 3.75 vol% voids (Table 2). The consistent v_f confirm that structural composites can be successfully produced by the processing and manufacturing route developed.

Matrix type	Fibre volume, V_f (%)	Matrix volume (%)	Void volume (%)
Control	54.3 ± 0.4	45.5 ± 0.5	0.2 ± 0.2
Homog. 2.4	51.1 ± 0.2	48.8 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.1
Homog. 4.8	52.7 ± 0.2	45.6 ± 0.4	1.8 ± 0.1
Homog. 9.1	55.2 ± 0.2	42.8 ± 0.3	2.1 ± 0.1
Homog. 20	49.6 ± 0.1	46.7 ± 0.2	3.8 ± 0.1
Hetero. 2.5 (1:1)	52.4 ± 0.4	47.1 ± 0.5	0.6 ± 0.2
Hetero. 7.5 (1:1)	53.0 ± 0.2	45.2 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.1
Hetero. 2.2 (5:1)	52.4 ± 0.3	46.7 ± 0.4	0.9 ± 0.1

Table 2: HC composition as determined by acid digestion.

The composite manufactured from the neat resin has an initiation G_{IC} of $600 \pm 20 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$ (Figure 1) which was improved by the homogeneous addition of CNTs to the matrix, except for the highest loading (20 wt%) which could not be fully consolidated. In the homogeneous matrix materials the

largest improvement of 12% was observed when adding 5 wt% CNTs. The Hetero 2.2 (5:1) composite exhibited the largest fracture toughness of $815 \pm 5 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$, a significant 36% improvement. Overall, the CNTs account for 2.2 wt% of the matrix in the Hetero 2.2 (5:1) composite, thus making the composite comparable with the homogeneous system containing 2.5 wt% CNTs and the Hetero 2.5 (1:1): the Hetero 2.2 (5:1) has a 30% larger G_{IC} than either of the similar systems. As such, the fracture toughness improvement can be attributed to the relative spacing of the CNT reinforced matrix region and the effect of the spacing on the crack path.

Figure 1: G_{IC} values of hierarchical composites as measured by DCB test. The strain energy release rate is presented against CNT content in the composite, which was deduced from the CNT content in the matrix and fibre volume fractions.

Scanning electron micrographs (Figure 2a) show clean fibres and tracks that the homogeneous HCs failed mainly adhesively at the fibre-matrix interface. On the other hand, the heterogeneous HCs exhibit a mix of adhesive and cohesive failure (Figure 2b), indicating increased crack path tortuosity relative to the homogeneous matrix composites. The improved Mode I fracture toughness can be attributed to the tortuous crack propagation as well as associated mechanisms such as crack deflection.

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of HCs manufactured from a) powder containing 2.4 wt% CNTs and b) a 5:1 powder blend of neat and 13 wt% CNT resins.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A powder based route for manufacturing HCs with large CNT loadings was modified to allow engineering of the matrix microstructure. Blending neat and nano-reinforced powders during impregnation has resulted in a heterogeneous microstructure through which cracks propagate adhesively as well as cohesively. The additional energy associated with the larger fracture surface area has yielded 36% improvement in Mode I fracture toughness, up to 815 Jm^{-2} .

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